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Research Article

**OCCURRENCE OF EMERGENCY OBSTETRIC
HYSTERECTOMY AND ASSOCIATED COMPLICATIONS**¹Dr Usama Ahmed Bakhtiari, ²Dr Bilal Ahsan, ³Dr Adnan Abbas Nizami¹Medical Officer, BHU Bakhtiari, Ahmad Pur East, Bahawalpur²Medical Officer Neurosurgery, Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Rahim Yar Khan³Medical officer, RHC Daud Khel Mianwali**Abstract:**

Objective: The aim of this research work is to find out the rate of incidence, associated complication and etiology of Emergency Obstetric Hysterectomy in Civil Hospital, Bahawalpur.

Methodology: This research work was a retroactive study conducted in the Obstetric Department of Civil Hospital, Bahawalpur from June 2017 to June 2019. All the patients who were scheduled to undergo emergency obstetric hysterectomy were the part of this research work. We collected the information from the registers of labor room and clinical files of the patients following the ethical instruction. The data contained the information about emergency obstetric hysterectomy causes, traits of demography, and method linked with the rate of morbidity and mortality. We collected the information on a Performa. SPSS V.18 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information.

Results: Total eight thousand deliveries took place in these years in which thirty-two patients underwent emergency obstetric hysterectomy. The rate of the incidence was 4.01 per one thousand births. The average age of the patients was 30 ± 5.20 years. Seventy-five percent females of this study were multipara. Cesarean Section was the main delivery mode (80.0%), and mostly it was performed as a procedure of emergency (81.0%). In 30.0% (n: 10) patients, emergency obstetric hysterectomy carried out due to not controllable hemorrhage of uterine atony. This was followed by the MAP (Morbidly Adherent Placenta) in twenty-eight percent patients. Morbidity contained Disseminated Intra-vascular coagulation in 19.0% (n: 4) patients (19%) and 3 patients had to undergo recurrent laparotomy due to hemorrhage which was not controllable. Three mothers died during this study providing an index of case-fatality as 9.30%.

Conclusion: MAP and uterine atony were the most important causes for the emergency obstetric hysterectomy in this current research work.

Keywords: Hemorrhage, Morbidity, Disseminated Intra-Vascular Coagulation, Emergency Obstetric Hysterectomy, Obstetric.

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INTRODUCTION:

Emergency Obstetric Hysterectomy is a lifesaving surgical intervention but it can lead to many complications. The most important reason of this procedure is the not controllable hemorrhage in the whole world, especially in the developing countries as Pakistan. A research work conducted in the past in our institution displayed that most leading cause of the high rate of maternal mortality was hemorrhage. Though hysterectomy in obstetrics was pioneered greater than two hundred years ago, it is still playing applicable role in the administration of the peri-partum hemorrhage, particularly in the countries which are under-development where there is no accessibility to the interventional radiology. Deficiency of infrastructure, late referrals also performs a vital role in high amount of the conservative procedures for the administration of the peri-partum hemorrhage contains utilization of prostaglandins, compression sutures and balloon tamponade. The initiation of these procedures has caused in the reduction of the rate of occurrence of the emergency obstetric hysterectomy. In the modern world, regardless of the advanced modalities like embolization of the uterine artery, emergency obstetric hysterectomy is the mainstay of therapy for the control of intractable hemorrhage.

The rate of occurrence of Emergency Obstetric Hysterectomy varies in the whole world with a range from 0.64 to 5.09 per one thousand deliveries. In the non-urban areas of our country Pakistan, most of the deliveries are performed by the unskillful birth attendants, which are the main reasons of the serious complication as rupture of uterine and obstructed labor which require emergency obstetric hysterectomy. This procedure also has association with the significant rate of maternal morbidity as well as maternal mortality in severe patients. This research work aimed to assess the rate of occurrence of emergency obstetric hysterectomy in Civil Hospital Bahawalpur and to find out the linked risk factors and associated complications.

METHODOLOGY:

This research work was retroactive study conducted from June 2017 to June 2019. All the patients who were in need of emergency obstetric hysterectomy because of not controllable hemorrhage in the Obstetric Department in Civil Hospital Bahawalpur were the part of this research work. This is a tertiary health care hospital handling the patients of city as well as from distant rural areas of the country. We collected the data from the files of hospital and admission registers of labor rooms following the regulations of the ethical committee. We defined the emergency obstetric hysterectomy as hysterectomy carried out after twenty-four weeks of the pregnancy period and within six weeks after the deliveries. We gathered the information about the age of the patients, parity number, etiology of the obstetric hemorrhage, signs for Cesarean Section, the proportion of the loss of blood and adverse incidents after the method including death or the admission in the ICU.

We were highly concern towards the clinical complication like DIC and other damage of any other organ. We collected the information in the well-organized Performa. SPSS V.18 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information. This was a retroactive research work, so we did not take any ethical approval for the conduction of this research work.

RESULTS:

In the duration of this research work, about eight thousand deliveries took place in this hospital in which thirty-two females underwent emergency obstetric hysterectomy. The rate of its incidence was 4.01 per one thousand deliveries. The traits of demography of these thirty-two females are present in Table-1.

Characteristics		No	Percent
Age	<20	2.0	6.25
	20-29	4.0	12.50
	30-35	16.0	50.00
	>35	10.0	31.00
Parity	1	1.0	3.10
	2 - 5	24.0	75.00
	>5	7.0	21.80
Mode of delivery	Vaginal delivery	6.0	18.75
	Emergency cesarean section	18.0	56.25
	Elective cesarean section	8.0	25.00
	Total cesarean sections	26.0	81.25

The average age of these females was 30.0 ± 5.20 years. The parity rate of most of the females was between two and five (75.0%). The main mode of deliveries in these patients was cesarean section (81.0%). Uterine atony causing the hemorrhage was very frequent indication (31.25%); this indication was followed by MAP (28.0%) as presented in Table-2.

Indication for Emergency Obstetric Hysterectomy	No	Percent
Uterine atony	10.0	31.30
Placenta previa	6.0	18.70
Secondary post-partum hemorrhage	2.0	6.20
Uterine rupture	5.0	15.60
Adherent placenta	9.0	28.10

The morbidity as associated with the emergency obstetric hysterectomy is present in Table-3. We identified one (3.0%) renal damage in surgical intervention; a urology specialist tackled that issue.

We discovered DIC in nineteen percent (n: 4) patients, there was a requirement of huge transfusion of blood in those patients. There was requirement of repeat laparotomy in 9.0% (n: 3) patients to control hemorrhage. The rate of mortality was 9.0% (n: 3). These females had to face heavy hemorrhage and finished in DIC in spite of the huge transfusion of blood. The other most reported problem in this subject matter is febrile morbidity [2], but we were unable to note this complication in this current research work.

Morbidity	No	Percentage
DIC	4.0	12.50
Urinary bladder injury	1.0	3.10
Repeat laparotomy	3.0	9.40
Wound infection	2.0	6.30
Intensive care stay	11.0	34.40
Death	3.0	9.40

DISCUSSION:

In the duration of this research work, total thirty-two patients underwent emergency obstetric hysterectomy. The incidence of emergency obstetric hysterectomy was 4.01 per one thousand deliveries. This rate is much higher in accordance with the available research as 0.680/1000 child births deliveries in Saudi Arabia, 0.250/1000 deliveries occurring in Taiwan, 5.09/1000 deliveries occurring in Turkey and 2.70/1000 deliveries in United States of America. The difference in the occurrence may be due to the health facilities present in those countries. In this research work, the most frequent reason of the emergency obstetric hysterectomy was the uterine atony followed by MAP. Uterine atony was also the most frequent cause of emergency obstetric hysterectomy in the research works of Varras and Rabiou. On the other hand, MAP and placenta Previa were the most common causes of emergency obstetric hysterectomy as mentioned in many other research works. One other research work from the private hospital discovered the MAP as the most common reason behind emergency obstetric hysterectomy. According to the authors, high rate of CS is the main reason for the high occurrence of the emergency obstetric hysterectomy. In one other research work conducted in the Sindh province of Pakistan discovered the uterine rupture as the most vital cause of emergency obstetric hysterectomy. MAP was the 2nd most important reason of the emergency obstetric hysterectomy in the patients of this research work with twenty-eight percent (n: 9) patients had to undergo emergency obstetric hysterectomy due to this very reason. In case of the peri-partum hemorrhage, it is much necessary to take effective and in time decision to save the life of the patients. This can prevent the high mortality rate as well as it also reduces the high morbidity linked with this procedure as prolonged duration of the surgery and the massive transfusion of the blood. The results of this research work are much consistent with the literature published in past as the CS has been declared as the most salient feature for the application of emergency obstetric hysterectomy. There should be an involvement of multidisciplinary approach containing surgeons, services of blood banks, midwives and nurses. The rise in the rate of CS has increased the complications as rupture of uterine, anomalous placentation which is an important reason for emergency obstetric hysterectomy. There are many complications in consequence of the emergency obstetric hysterectomy. Most common complications are injury to the urinary tract and near objects. Some other associated complications are infections of wounds, obstruction in intestines which can require

another laparotomy in the patients with severe condition. This research work is based on the data of single hospital, most of the patients were referrals in emergency state and most of the records of the patients were not complete; these are some limitation of this research work.

CONCLUSION:

The most frequent reasons of emergency obstetric hysterectomy as diagnosed in this research work were MAP and uterine atony.

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